

**NATIONAL-CULTURAL SPECIFICITY OF MAGICAL
NUMBERS IN UZBEK AND ENGLISH FOLK TALES****Sayfiddinova Munisa Fahriddin kizi**

Researcher, Namangan State University

Teacher, Turan International University

Email: msayfiddinova94@gmail.com

Phone: +99 890 215 48 77

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20019365>**ARTICLE INFO**Received: 26th April 2026Accepted: 28th April 2026Online: 30th April 2026**KEYWORDS**

magical numbers, folklore, Uzbek fairy tales, English fairy tales, national specificity, semantics, mythology, cultural code, universality

ABSTRACT

This article provides a comparative analysis of the national specificity of magical numbers in Uzbek and English folk tales. It reveals the semantic and functional features of the numbers 3, 7, 9, 12, and 40. The results of the study show that in Uzbek folklore numbers are more associated with ritual and educational meanings, whereas in English folklore they express individual trials and cosmic order.

The national characteristics of magical numbers are primarily determined by each people's religious beliefs and mythological worldview. For example, in Uzbek folklore, a numerical system formed on the basis of Islamic worldview predominates, while in English folklore, numbers connected with Christianity, ancient Germanic mythology, and Celtic traditions are more common. In Uzbek folk tales, numbers such as 3, 7, 9, and 40 and their derivatives (14, 18, 41, 90, 99, etc.) mainly originate under the influence of the religious and mythological concepts of Turkic peoples. In contrast, in English folk tales, the numbers 3, 7, and 12 receive particular attention due to the influence of Christianity and European mythology. These differences demonstrate that magical numbers also carry a national-semantic load.

In particular, in Uzbek folk tales, magical numbers are closely connected with Islamic, Sufi, and Eastern mythological views. The numbers 7, 40, and 9 have deeply rooted meanings in народное consciousness. The number 40 in Uzbek folk tales appears in combinations such as "forty days," "forty saints," and "forty-day wedding," symbolizing completeness, trial, and sacred time. This number does not appear in English fairy tales, which reflects the unique features of Uzbek national thinking.

Another important aspect is that in Uzbek folk tales numbers are often used for moral and educational purposes. For example, expressions such as knowing seven generations, three pieces of advice, and nine virtues are directly related to upbringing. In everyday folk speech, instead of using exact arithmetic numbers, traditional symbolic numbers are employed to express the concept of multiplicity. For example: "seven robbers," "forty young men," "forty days and nights of celebration" [10, p. 50].

The analysis of Uzbek folk tale materials shows that within the widely used system of magical numbers, the number 7 occupies a special place. While acquiring universality, it also

carries a national-cultural code, reflecting the specific features of Uzbek culture in numerous expressions and folklore samples. The widespread use of the magical number 7 is explained by its special significance in ancient Uzbek folklore and customs. Ancient beliefs about the sacred nature of the number 7 are preserved in proverbs such as “Measure seven times, cut once,” “The right of an orphan can dry up seven rivers,” in riddles like “It has a small body but wears seven layers of clothing,” and in place names such as Yettisuv, Yettiqashqa, Yettikechuv, Yettisoy, Yettiqiz, as well as in beliefs about the constellation of the Seven Thieves (Ursa Major). A poetic system of images such as seven generations, seven ancestors, seven relatives, seven brothers, seven sisters, seven companions, seven robbers, seven thieves, seven demons, seven witches, and seven envoys is based on the magical nature of the number 7. This number has been considered sacred since ancient times, and its deep integration into everyday speech and various aspects of life is largely due to the role of folklore.

In English oral tradition, magical numbers are mainly shaped under the influence of Christianity and European mythology. The number 3, in particular, is widely used as a symbol of sacredness and perfection. This is directly connected with the concept of the Holy Trinity (Father, Son, Holy Spirit) in the Bible. The number 3 is also considered a universal semantic sign, as it is actively used in the folklore of many peoples.

In addition to the number 3, the number 7 is also one of the most widespread and deeply rooted numbers in English folklore. It represents the complete cycle of an event and serves as a model of completion and perfect order, which originates from the Biblical concept of the creation of the world in seven days. The number 7 can be associated with concepts of the structure of the universe and may function as a model expressing cosmic harmony. In fairy tales, it is also widely used as a sign of magic, supernatural power, multiplicity, and transformation. In English folk tales, magical numbers are more closely associated with individualism and personal trials. For example, the hero's passing through three or seven trials demonstrates their personal maturity. This reflects the importance of personal freedom and individual success in English mentality. In rituals, numbers such as 3 and 7 are actively used, and in some traditions, repeating an action three times is believed to bring good luck.

One of the most frequently used numbers in Uzbek folklore, especially in fairy tales, is 40, which has a special symbolic and mythopoetic significance. It is not merely a quantitative marker but a semantic unit expressing concepts such as long duration, trial, multiplicity, and sacredness. The genesis of this number dates back to ancient Turkic religious, mythological, and ritual beliefs. The number 40 symbolizes divinity, maturity, and purification. The well-known Turkish writer Elif Shafak also highlights the significance of the number 40 in Turkic culture in her book *The Forty Rules of Love*, where she associates it with maturity, purification, and spiritual awakening [4, p. 125].

Among Muslims, the number 40 holds particular importance: the Prophet Muhammad (peace be upon him) received revelation at the age of forty, and the number of his early followers was also forty. Furthermore, giving one-fortieth of one's wealth as zakat, and the numerical value of the Arabic letter “mim” corresponding to forty, further reinforce its significance. In shamanistic beliefs, it is believed that the soul leaves the body forty days after death. Even today, customs such as observing a forty-day mourning period and the ritual of “forty days after death” originate from these beliefs.

In fairy tales, the number 40 represents long duration, completion, major trials, and victory. It symbolizes patience, courage, and spiritual elevation. For example, in the tale “Forty Grooms,” expressions such as forty grooms and forty girls appear [8, pp. 66–67]. In “Three Brave Brothers,” “forty days and nights of celebration” is mentioned [11, p. 15]. In “Tohir and Zuhra,” mourning lasts for forty days [11, p. 15]. In “The King and the Parrot,” a forty-day deadline is given as a test [9, p. 95].

These examples clearly demonstrate that the number 40 in Uzbek folk tales performs multiple linguopoetic and linguocultural functions. It symbolizes multiplicity, completeness, ritual duration, and transitional phases. It functions not merely as a number but as a universal poetic device expressing cultural meanings.

According to some sources, the number 12 in Uzbek folklore represents order, perfection, and cosmic harmony. It often signifies the completeness of time and space cycles (e.g., twelve months). Similarly, in English folklore, it structures narrative elements such as twelve knights or twelve tasks. In the Bible, the number 12 symbolizes divine order, as reflected in the twelve apostles [12, Chapter 10; 3, pp. 190–195]. For example, in “The Maiden Who Seeks her Brothers,” twelve brothers symbolize a complete family structure and are transformed into ravens [1, p. 153]. In English folklore collections by Joseph Jacobs, expressions such as “twelve months,” “twelve golden pillars,” and “twelve o’clock” represent cosmic order, boundaries, and transformation [5, p. 64; 6, p. 18].

The analysis of these examples shows that magical numbers in folklore embody mythological, cosmological, and structural elements such as epic composition, repetition, and symbolic imagery. They organize narrative structure, enrich сюжет, and reflect ancient worldviews.

Conclusion

Based on the analysis, magical numbers in Uzbek and English folklore serve as important symbolic units reflecting national culture and mentality. While some numbers demonstrate universality, their semantic interpretation and functional load are determined by national characteristics. In Uzbek folklore, magical numbers are mainly associated with Islamic-Sufi, ritual, and educational meanings, whereas in English folklore they are linked to Christianity and individualistic views. The study of magical numbers is essential for understanding cultural codes in folklore.

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